

Appendices belonging to Chapter 4 of the PhD-thesis entitled "Sustainability and resilience of European farming systems: an integrated assessment".

Supplementary Materials 4.1. Number of observations

As the number of observed years differed per farm, the number of observations per year included in the analysis differed (Table A1, Table A2).

Table A1.1. Number of observations per year for the three case study regions.

Region	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
FL	9	12	14	15	15	15	15	15	14	14	14	12	10	10
ZE	14	16	15	16	17	17	16	17	15	15	15	15	15	15
VK	13	14	14	16	19	19	19	19	17	17	17	16	17	15

Table A1.2. Years per farm per region for which observations are available for all variables included in the sPLS analyses.

Farm code	Region	'06	'07	'08	'09	'10	'11	'12	'13	'14	'15	'16	'17	'18	'19
87279	FL	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA
87280	FL	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA
87282	FL	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
87540	FL	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
87541	FL	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
87544	FL	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
87553	FL	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
87559	FL	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
87569	FL	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
87285	FL	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
87286	FL	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
87287	FL	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
87289	FL	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA
87290	FL	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
87571	FL	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA
49822	ZE	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49826	ZE	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
49851	ZE	1	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49857	ZE	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49861	ZE	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49875	ZE	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
49895	ZE	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49909	ZE	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49947	ZE	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49950	ZE	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49954	ZE	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49955	ZE	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49957	ZE	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49960	ZE	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49977	ZE	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49980	ZE	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
49985	ZE	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21581	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21650	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA
21658	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
21812	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21813	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA

21816	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21823	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
21834	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21840	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21866	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21867	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21869	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
33579	VK	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21906	VK	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21925	VK	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21936	VK	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21926	VK	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
21933	VK	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1
21938	VK	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Supplementary Materials 4.2. Details on variables

Overview

Table A2.1. Overview of means, standard deviations and trends (for continuous variables if $p < 0.05$) of Y and X-Variables per region. Slope in the table heading refers to a linear regression over the data.

Type of variable	Sub-category (1st)	Sub-category (2nd)	Abbreviation	Unit	FL			VK			ZE		
					Mean	SD	slope	Mean	SD	slope	Mean	SD	Slope
Response variables	Output efficiency		OutputEff	€ output/€ input	112	24	-	105	22	0	102	24	-
			OutputEff_resi	€ output/€ input	0.1	19.0	-	0.0	9.0	-	-0.1	18.9	-
			OutputEff_slope	€/€/year	0.02	1.37	0.005	0.80	5.897	-0.986	-0.994	1.873	-
	Potato yield		PotatoYield	kg / ha	48947	8472	-334	42249	5525	-242	43513	9780	-464
			PotatoYield_resi	kg / ha	5	3465	-	-10	4242	-	-42	6130	-
			PotatoYield_slope	kg / ha / year	-148	1146	3	-251	1111	-	-509	453	-
	Crop rotation energy yield		CropRotYield	kJ / ha	191228	35853	393	186749	25974	-	174478	29432	-
			CropRotYield_resi	kJ / ha	103	13197	-	-222	16234	-	-52	15516	-
			CropRotYield_slope	kJ / ha / year	-114	8346	-223	2290	3383	-294	1144	3364	-
	Profit crops		ProfitCrops	€/ha	5347	1726	119	1619	495	-	2868	1419	-4
			ProfitCrops_resi	€/ha	8	1237	-	-2	251	-	-3	876	-
			ProfitCrops_slope	€ / ha / year	99	105	2	48	140	-	3	46	-
	Nitrogen surplus		Nsurplus	kg / ha	107.8	61.1	4.2	96.8	42.6	-	121.9	58.3	-0.1
			Nsurplus_resi	kg/ha	0.1	49.3	-	0.2	22.6	-	-0.2	42.1	-

		Nsurplus_slope	kg / ha / year	3.4	5.8	0.2	-3.3	14.1	0.7	-0.7	5.8	-		
				FL			VK			ZE				
Type of variable	Sub-category (1st)	Sub-category (2nd)	Abbreviation	Unit	Mean	SD	slope	Mean	SD	slope	Mean	SD	Slope	
Explanatory variable	Farm characteristics	Land use	AreaCereals	ha	0.20	0.11	0.00	0.28	0.10	-	0.30	0.13	-	
			AreaMainCrops	ha	0.48	0.25	-	0.91	0.08	-	0.59	0.19	-	
			TrueDiversity	#	3.64	0.84	-0.02	3.23	0.50	-	4.43	1.23	-	
	Input intensity			Monetary input* intensity	€ input/cultivated ha	7281	1581	154	3352	804	77	4560	1179	109
				Labour	AWU / cultivated ha	0.03	0.01	-	0.01	0.007	-	0.0166	0.005	-
				Crop Protection Product (CPP)	€/ cultivated ha	607.3	145.4	19.3	394.0	104.4	15.1	435.1	156.4	13.2
				Nitrogen	€/ cultivated ha	256.6	76.3	-	225.6	53.5	-	254.9	64.8	0.2
				Phosphate	€/ cultivated ha	81.7	25.6	-1.0	74.7	24.8	-	68.8	25.2	-0.8
				Energy	€/ cultivated ha	182.7	94.4	-	20.4	14.9	-	83.2	58.7	0.5
				TotalCostsperha**	€/ cultivated ha	2025.7	583.2	57.1	871.1	205.4	38.7	1398.8	592.4	41.9
	Management			FarmManagement	# managers / ha	0.03	0.02	-0.001	0.02	0.01	-	0.01	0.01	0.0002
				AgeFarmer	Years	52.8	8.6	-	54.8	9.3	0.2	48.3	9.2	0.7
				OtherRevenue	€/ cultivated ha	1136	726	-	1081	494	3	738	335	16
	Assets			Area	ha	120.1	105.9	2.5	130.3	109.4	4.7	127.8	53.8	-
				AreaOwned	owned ha / total ha	0.58	0.27	-	0.76	0.24	-	0.61	0.31	-

Type of variable	Sub-category (1st)	Sub-category (2nd)	Abbreviation	Unit	Mean	SD	slope	Mean	SD	slope	Mean	SD	Slope
			OwnCapital	€ own / € total assets	66.3	19.4	-	76.6	13.4	-	80.4	10.3	-
					FL			VK			ZE		
			ModernityBuildings	# (0-100)	45.4	15.2	-0.4	43.7	17.5	-	48.2	17.6	-
			ModernityMachines	# (0-100)	37.9	11.6	-	38.4	11.9	-0.2	36.2	11.0	-0.7
			Depreciation	€ / cultivated ha	1261	503	65	488	231	29	676	372	42
	Weather conditions	Average	Tempreature_Spring	degree Celcius	13.3	1.1	-	13.0	1.1	-	13.6	1.0	-
			Precipitation_Spring	mm / day	1.6	0.5	-	1.6	0.4	-	1.6	0.5	-
			PrecDef_Spring	mm / day	1.5	0.6	-	1.5	0.6	-	1.5	0.7	-
			Tempreature_Summer	degree Celcius	17.1	0.8	-	16.9	0.7	-	17.7	0.8	-
			Precipitation_Summer	mm / day	2.6	0.8	-	2.3	0.7	-	2.3	0.7	-
			PrecDef_Summer	mm / day	0.3	1.0	-	0.6	0.9	-	0.8	0.9	-
			Temperature	degree celcius	10.6	0.7	-	10.3	0.7	-	11.4	0.7	-
			Precipitation	mm / day	2.1	0.3	-	2.0	0.3	-	2.0	0.2	-
			PrecDef	mm / day	-0.2	0.3	-	-0.1	0.4	-	0.0	0.3	-
		Extremes***	ExtPrec45_1	# / 14 year	0			0			0		
			ExtPrec60_3	# / 14 year	1			0			2		
			HWave	# / 14 year	6			8			4		
			Frost	# / 14 year	0			0			0		

Type of variable	Sub-category (1st)	Sub-category (2nd)	Abbreviation	Unit	FL Mean	SD	slope	VK Mean	SD	slope	ZE Mean	SD	Slope
			WarmWinter	# / 14 year	5			4			9		
			WarmWet	# / 14 year	17			12			19		
			D_Spring	# / 14 year	2			2			2		
			D_Summer	# / 14 year	3			2			4		
			WetHumPlant	# / 14 year	29			22			32		
			WetHumGrow	# / 14 year	15			17			14		
			WetHumHarv	# / 14 year	13			12			11		
	Market****		OilPrice	€/ 100 L	88	17	3	88	17	3	88	17	3
			FertilizerPrice	€/ 100 kg	43	8	-	43	8	-	43	8	-
			LandPrice	€/ha	57194	8065	1786	57194	8065	1786	57194	8065	1786
			Interest rate	%	2.1	1.6	-0.4	2.1	1.6	-0.4	2.1	1.6	-0.4

*Monetary input at farm level, i.e. all fixed and variable costs.**Cultivation costs, i.e. variable costs for crop cultivation. ***See Table A2.3 for more information.

****See Table A2.2 for more information

Market conditions

Table A2.2. Absolute values of market indicators included in the analyses: interest rate (OECD, 2021), oil price (WEcR, 2020), fertilizer price (WEcR, 2020) and land price (Kadaster, 2021).

	Land price (€/ha)	Interest rate (%)	Oil Price (€/ 100 L)	Fertilizer price (€/ 100 kg)
2006	44506	3.78	64	27.35
2007	48076	4.29	65	27.75
2008	54967	4.23	81	48.00
2009	53183	3.69	61	61.50
2010	53856	2.99	74	41.25
2011	52339	2.99	90	44.00
2012	50964	1.93	96	45.55
2013	53809	1.96	110	45.05
2014	56758	1.45	109	44.65
2015	60644	0.69	94	47.00
2016	65695	0.29	87	46.60
2017	65480	0.52	94	42.45
2018	69004	0.58	103	41.95
2019	71440	-0.07	105	42.95

Weather extremes

Average weather conditions were calculated based on a 25x25km grid weather data from Agri4cast. The overlay of 25*25km grids with the case study regions was calculated using ArcGIS-pro. A weighted average based on the calculated overlay was used to calculate the weather conditions for the case study areas. Average weather conditions included in the analysis were average temperature (degree Celsius), average daily precipitation (mm/day) and average daily precipitation deficit (mm/day) for the whole year, spring (April-June) and summer (July-September). The precipitation deficit is calculated as the amount of precipitation minus the daily reference evapotranspiration as provided by the Agri4cast data.

Table A2.3. Weather extremes for potato production based on the AgroClimateCalendar. Source: adapted from Schaap et al. (2011, 2013).

Extreme event	Abbreviation	Period	Definition	Effect
Extreme precipitation	ExtPrec45_1 or ExtrPrec60_3	May-September	>45 mm in 1 day or >60 mm in 2 days	Water logging and rotting of tubers
Wet/humid planting phase	WetHumPlant	October-April	> 0.75 mm / day for 21 subsequent days	Problems with sowing green manure and planting seed potatoes
Wet/humid growing phase	WetHumGrow	May-August	> 0.75 mm / day for 21 subsequent days	Difficulties spraying against phytophthora
Wet/humid harvesting phase	WetHumHarv	August-October	> 0.75 mm / day for 21 subsequent days	Difficulties harvesting the crop
Heatwave	HWave	July-August	> 25 °C for 5 days of which 3 days > 30 °C	Second growth reducing yield and quality
Late frost	Frost	April-May	< -2 °C for 2 subsequent days	Damage of young crop
Warm winter	WarmWinter	December-March	> 10 °C for 14 subsequent days	More rotting of tubers in storage and early sprouting in March
Warm and wet	WarmWet	July-September	> 20 °C and > 0 mm / day for 14 subsequent days	Increased prevalence of plant disease
Drought in spring*	D_Spring	February-April	< 5 mm precipitation in 30 subsequent days	Water stress affecting general plant development
Drought in summer*	D_Summer	May-September	< 10 mm precipitation in 30 subsequent days	Water stress affecting tuber development

*Originally drought was not included in the ACC as an extreme event for potato production in the Netherlands.

Table A2.4. Occurrence of weather extremes in the three case studies from 2006 till 2019.

Year	Region	ExtPrec 45_1	ExtPrec 60_3	HWave	Frost	Warm Winter	Warm Wet	D_ Spring	D_ Summer	WetHum Plant	WetHum Grow
2006	FL	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	1	1	2
2007	FL	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	4	2
2008	FL	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1
2009	FL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
2010	FL	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	2	1
2011	FL	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	2
2012	FL	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	1
2013	FL	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	4	1
2014	FL	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	2	1
2015	FL	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	3	0
2016	FL	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	3	2
2017	FL	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
2018	FL	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	4	0
2019	FL	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	1	1
2006	VK	0	0	2	0	1	1	0	0	2	2
2007	VK	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	1
2008	VK	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2
2009	VK	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
2010	VK	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	1	2	1
2011	VK	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	2
2012	VK	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	1
2013	VK	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0
2014	VK	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	3	2
2015	VK	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	1
2016	VK	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	2
2017	VK	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2018	VK	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	2	0
2019	VK	0	0	2	0	1	2	0	0	1	2
2006	ZE	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	2
2007	ZE	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	3	2
2008	ZE	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	2
2009	ZE	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
2010	ZE	0	1	0	0	2	2	0	0	2	0
2011	ZE	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	1
2012	ZE	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	2	2
2013	ZE	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	0
2014	ZE	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	3	1
2015	ZE	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	1
2016	ZE	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	3	1
2017	ZE	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0
2018	ZE	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	2	3	0
2019	ZE	0	0	2	0	1	2	0	1	3	1

Supplementary Materials 4.3. Details on methods

Threshold regression

Linear trendlines can be considered when at least three data points are available. Given the minimum length of the time series data (seven years), only one structural change in trend was considered in between the third from first and third from last observation. To ensure that observed structural changes were not dependent on a single outlier, two additional two-segmented linear regression analyses were performed. In these additional threshold regressions either the last observation of the first segment or the first observation in the second line segment was removed. A structural change in trend, and thus a two-segmented model, was accepted and used for further analyses if the p-values of the F-statistics for the optimum breaking point of all three threshold regressions stayed below 0.05. Otherwise a linear regression with one segment was assumed. Regression analyses with structural change tests were performed with the package "strucchange" (Zeileis et al., 2002) in the software environment R (R Core Team, 2015).

Principal component analyses

A multi-level design was included to consider the random effects of individual farms. As a result, we argue, farm specific differences will be compensated for, thus reducing the impact of outliers for which multi-variate statistics are sensitive (Alvarez et al., 2018). The first three components of PCA biplots were inspected to detect farms for which all observations were visually separated from the rest of the observations. Those outlying farms were removed from the dataset (only one in FL). PCA biplots were also inspected for the presence of year effects. The presence of a year effect in the PCA-analyses was used as an argument for including random year effects in further analyses. Highly correlated response variables were avoided in further analysis as they can distort the analysis (Whuber, 2013). We illustrate this by presenting additional model runs including highly correlated response variables (Appendix 5).

Details on sparse Partial Least Squares

We used (sparse) Partial Least Squares regression ((s)PLS) with year and farms as random effects to study the impact of explanatory variables on the response variables. In (s)PLS-regressions, explanatory variables (X-variables) are projected on latent variables in such a way that the projected variables can explain as much variation of the response variables (Y-variables) that are also projected on latent variables. We used sPLS in a regression mode, where the prediction of Y from X results in different identified latent variables than when X would be predicted from Y. This limits the possibility to make inferences on adaptations in X related to observed changes in Y, e.g. changes in inputs as a consequence of a year with low economic performance. Redundancy analysis, in contrast to PLS analysis, only projects X-Variables on latent variables, but leaves the Y-Variables as they are.

Leave-one-out cross-validations were conducted to determine the performance of the (s)PLS-model. Resulting Q²- and R²-scores were used to determine the number of latent variables (components) in the PLS-result that can help to reveal the underlying data structure. Q²-scores express the marginal contribution of components to increase the covariation between X- and Y-Variables. A component with a Q²-score larger than 0.095 is considered to have a significant contribution. (Lê Cao et al., 2008).

Sparse PLS (sPLS) differs from PLS in that it reduces the model to a pre-defined number of variables that are linked to principal components in the X and Y dimensions. The advantage of sPLS is that interpreting results is becoming easier. A disadvantage is that choosing the number of variables per component introduces arbitrariness. We performed multiple sPLS analyses in which we varied the number of Y-Variables (2-5) and X-Variables (2-9) per component. To reduce computation time, we initially limited the number of components to two. We selected the best model based on the aggregated Q²-score and explained variance of X- and Y-Variables. We also checked the stability of X- and Y-Variables selected in the sPLS-models during the cross-validation. In case the second component was contributing significantly, analyses with a third component were considered, for (2-5) Y-Variables and (2-9) X-Variables. In case the third component contributed significantly, the number of X- and Y-Variables to keep was selected on the same criteria as for the first two components. We used the performance levels

of a PLS model as a reference to reflect on the changed data projections of the final sPLS-models presented in this study.

PCA and (s)PLS were performed with the software package "mixOmics" (Cao et al., 2017) in the software environment R (R Core Team, 2015). "mixOmics" does not facilitate the inclusion of interaction terms.

Supplementary Materials 4.4. Results threshold regression

The threshold regression reveals interesting details in the data. Breaks in trend can be seen as consequences of internal or external changes. In this study we didn't specifically assess the cause of observed breaks in trends. The break in trend around 2012 may be related to the introduction of the new Common Agricultural Policy, which was perceived as having potentially large impacts on the farming system VK. Breaks in trend may be an interesting categorizing variable, for instance to compare the means of farm characteristics as is done in Sneessens et al. (2019). A larger dataset may be necessary for this. In our example for instance, the groups with and without breaks in trends were not balanced.

Table A4.1. Counts of farms and the median year for which a break in trend was observed for the observed values of OutputEff, PotatoYield, CropRotYield, ProfitCrops and Nsurplus in each region.

CS	Output efficiency		Potato Yield		Crop Rotation Yield		Crop profit		Nitrogen surplus	
	Trend break (#)	Year (median)	Trend break (#)	Year (median)	Trend break (#)	Year (median)	Trend break (#)	Year (median)	Trend break (#)	Year (median)
FL	0	-	2	2010	2	2012	0	-	2	2012
VK	15	2012	2	2011.5	2	2012.5	12	2011	5	2012
ZE	1	2012	0	-	1	2016	0	-	2	2011

Supplementary Materials 4.5. Results PCA

PCA Response Variables

FL

Figure A5.1. PCA results on response variables in FL for the first and second component. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

Figure A5.2. PCA results on response variables in FL for the first and third component. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

ZE

Figure A5.3. PCA results on response variables in ZE for the first and second component. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

Figure A5.4. PCA results on response variables in ZE for the first and third component. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

VK

Figure A5.5. PCA results on response variables in VK for the first and second component. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

Figure A5.6. PCA results on response variables in VK for the first and third component. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

PCA Farm variables

FL (with outlier)

Figure A5.7. PCA results on farm characteristic explanatory variables in FL for the first and third component **with the outlier included**. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

Figure A5.8. PCA results on farm characteristic explanatory variables in FL for the first and third component **with the outlier included**. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

FL

Figure A5.9. PCA results on farm characteristic explanatory variables in FL for the first and second component. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

Figure A5.10. PCA results on farm characteristic explanatory variables in FL for the first and third component. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

ZE

Figure A5.11. PCA results on farm characteristic explanatory variables in ZE for the first and second component. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

Figure A5.12. PCA results on farm characteristic explanatory variables in ZE for the first and third component. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

VK

Figure A5.13. PCA results on farm characteristic explanatory variables in VK for the first and second component. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

Figure A5.14. PCA results on farm characteristic explanatory variables in VK for the first and third component. Only variables with loadings > 0.4 are included.

Appendix 6. Results sPLS-models

FL

Table A6.1. Loadings and stability of response variables associated with the selected sPLS-components.

Response variable	Loadings		Stability	
	1 st component	2 nd component	1 st component	2 nd component
CropRotYield	0.49	0	1.00	0
CropRotYield_slope	-0.47	0	0	0
CropRotYield_resi	0	0	0	0
ProfitCrops	-0.65	0	1.00	0.02
ProfitCrops_slope	0	0	0.98	0
ProfitCrops_resi	0	-0.44	0	0.98
Nsurplus	0	0	0.02	0.02
Nsurplus_slope	0.35	0	1.00	0
Nsurplus_resi	0	0.90	0	0.98

Table A6.2. Loadings and stability of explanatory variables associated with the selected sPLS-components.

Explanatory variable	Loadings		Stability	
	1 st component	2 nd component	1 st component	2 nd component
Area	0	0	0	0
AreaOwned	0	0	0	0
AreaCereals	0	0	0.02	0
AreaMainCrops	0	0	0.02	0.01
Intensity	-0.68	0	1	0.02
Labour	0	0	0	0
CPP	-0.17	0	0.98	0.02
Nitrogen	0.24	0	1	0.03
Phosphate	0	0	0.02	0
FarmManagement	0	0	0	0
AgeFarmer	0	0	0	0
Energy	-0.15	0	0.98	0.02
Depreciation	-0.42	0	0.98	0.02
OtherRevenue	0	0	0	0
OwnCapital	0	0	0	0
ModernityBuildings	0	0	0	0
ModernityMachinery	0	0	0	0
TotalCostsperha	0	0	0	0.02
TrueDiversity	0.50	0	1	0
Temperature_Spring	0	0.43	0	0.98
Precipitation_Spring	0	0.31	0	0.98
Temperature_Summer	0	-0.09	0	0.97
Precipitation_Summer	0	0	0	0
PrecDef_Summer	0	0	0	0
PrecDef_Spring	0	-0.09	0	0.98
Temperature	0	0.21	0	0.98
Precipitation	0	0	0	0
PrecDef	0	0	0	0
ExtrPrec60_3	0	0.35	0	0.98
HWave	0	-0.25	0	0.98
WarmWinter	0	0	0	0
WarmWet	0	0	0	0
D_Spring	0	0.59	0	0.98
D_Summer	0	0	0	0
WetHumPlant	0	0	0	0
WetHumGrow	0	0.35	0	0.98
WetHumHarv	0	0	0	0
OilPrice	0	0	0	0.02

FertilizerPrice	0	0	0	0
Landprice	0	0	0	0.02
Interest	0	0	0	0.02

Table A6.3. Average values of response variables, weather conditions and extreme events associated with the second sPLS-component in FL. Values between brackets indicate the loading of variables on the component. Bold font of weather variables indicates above median weather conditions or occurrence of extreme events. Bold font of response variables indicates an above median absolute value. The bold font is applied to help evaluating whether extremes coincide with the most important weather condition (in this case "Average temperature in spring").

	Nsurplus_resi Kg/ha (0.90)	ProfitCropsperha_resi Eur/ha (-0.44)	Average temperature in spring °C (0.43)	Precipitation in spring mm/day (0.31)	Average Temperature °C (0.21)	Temperature in summer (- 0.09)	Precipitation deficit in summer (- 0.09)	Drought in spring #(0.59)	Extreme precipitation # (0.35)	WetHumGrow # (0.35)
2006	-11.1	1187	13.1	1.5	11.1	18.9	0.7	0	0	2
2007	30.2	-685	14.6	2.1	11.1	16.1	-0.3	1	0	2
2008	-15.7	-779	13.3	1.0	10.5	16.6	-0.5	0	0	1
2009	-0.4	112	13.7	1.7	10.4	17.3	1.4	0	0	1
2010	-13.3	1145	11.7	1.2	8.7	16.7	-1.1	0	0	1
2011	20.6	-1562	14.2	1.6	10.7	16.2	-0.9	1	1	2
2012	-8.7	1385	12.5	2.2	10.1	16.6	-0.1	0	0	1
2013	-1.9	639	11.5	1.7	9.6	17.0	1.1	0	0	1
2014	-2.8	-1116	13.7	2.3	11.7	17.5	0.5	0	0	1
2015	-13.6	400	12.0	1.1	10.8	16.9	-0.4	0	0	0
2016	21.2	-549	13.3	2.4	10.6	17.9	1.4	0	0	2
2017	5.1	-1144	13.8	1.5	10.9	16.6	-0.7	0	0	0
2018	4.8	1601	15.5	1.3	11.3	17.9	2.2	0	0	0
2019	-13.8	-40	13.4	1.5	11.1	17.5	1	0	0	1

Figure A6.1. sPLS model results for the first and second X-component in FL.

Figure A6.2. sPLS model results for the first and second Y-component in FL.

Figure A6.3. Correlations between explanatory and response variables selected by the sPLS-model in FL

ZE

Table A6.4. Loadings and stability of response variables associated with the selected SPLS-components in ZE.

Response variable	Loadings		Stability	
	1 st component	2 nd component	1 st component	2 nd component
CropRotYield	-0.25	0	1.00	0
CropRotYield_slope	0	0	0	0
CropRotYield_resi	0	0	0	0
ProfitCrops	0.78	-0.42	1.00	1.00
ProfitCrops_slope	-0.52	0	1.00	0
ProfitCrops_resi	0	-0.91	0	1.00
Nsurplus	-0.08	0	1.00	0
Nsurplus_slope	0.23	0	1.00	0
Nsurplus_resi	0	0	0	0

Table A6.5. Loadings and stability of explanatory variables associated with the selected SPLS-components in ZE.

Explanatory variable	Loadings		Stability	
	1 st component	2 nd component	1 st component	2 nd component
Area	0	0	0	0
AreaOwned	0	0	0	0
AreaCereals	0	0	0	0
AreaMainCrops	0	0	0	0
Intensity	0.48	0	1	0
Labour	0	0	0	0
CPP	0	0	0	0
Nitrogen	0	0	0	0
Phosphate	0	0	0	0
FarmManagement	0	0	0	0
AgeFarmer	0	0	0	0
Energy	0	0	0	0
Depreciation	0	0	0	0
OtherRevenue	0	0	0	0
OwnCapital	0	0	0	0
ModernityBuildings	0	0	0	0
ModernityMachinery	0	0	0	0
TotalCostsperha	0.88	0	1	0
TrueDiversity	0	0	0	0
Temperature_Spring	0	0.54	0	1
Precipitation_Spring	0	0	0	0
Temperature_Summer	0	0	0	0
Precipitation_Summer	0	0	0	0
PrecDef_Summer	0	0	0	0
PrecDef_Spring	0	0.19	0	1
Temperature	0	0.36	0	1
Precipitation	0	0	0	0
PrecDef	0	0	0	0
ExtrPrec60_3	0	0	0	0
HWave	0	0	0	0
WarmWinter	0	-0.74	0	1
WarmWet	0	0	0	0
D_Spring	0	0	0	0
D_Summer	0	0	0	0
WetHumPlant	0	0	0	0
WetHumGrow	0	0	0	0
WetHumHarv	0	0	0	0

OilPrice	0	0	0	0
FertilizerPrice	0	0	0	0
Landprice	0	0	0	0
Interest	0	0	0	0

Table A6.6. Average values of response variables, weather conditions and extreme events associated with the second sPLS-component in ZE. Values between brackets indicate the loading of variables on the component. Bold font of weather variables indicates above median weather conditions or occurrence of extreme events. Bold font of response variables indicates an above median absolute value. The bold font is applied to help evaluating whether extremes coincide with the most important weather condition (in this case "Average temperature in spring").

	ProfitCropsperha_resi €/ha (-0.91)	ProfitCropsperha €/ha (-0.42)	Average temp spring (0.54)	Temperature (0.36)	Precipitation deficit spring mm/day (0.19)	Warm winter (-0.74)
2006	580	9.7	13.1	11.7	1.2	1
2007	-557	-13.2	14.9	11.8	1.3	0
2008	-390	-7.5	13.6	11.1	1.7	0
2009	-241	-3.9	13.9	11.1	1.4	0
2010	1107	26.3	12.5	9.8	2.2	2
2011	-1131	-26.5	14.9	11.7	2.4	0
2012	1275	29.1	12.6	10.9	0.2	1
2013	-203	-3.7	11.6	10.3	1.0	0
2014	-677	-14.0	14.0	12.3	1.5	1
2015	300	6.4	12.8	11.5	2.2	1
2016	478	8.1	13.3	11.5	0.5	2
2017	-907	-16.6	14.3	11.8	2.4	0
2018	172	3.3	15.1	11.9	1.9	0
2019	192	1.7	13.7	11.8	1.8	1

Figure A6.4. sPLS model results for the first and second X-component in ZE.

Figure A6.5. sPLS model results for the first and second Y-component in ZE.

Figure A6.6. Correlations between explanatory and response variables selected by the SPLS-model in ZE.

Table A6.7. Loadings and stability of response variables associated with the selected sPLS-components in VK.

Response variable	Loadings per component			Stability per component		
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	1 st	2 nd	3 rd
CropRotYield	0	0	-0.61	0	0	1
CropRotYield_slope	0.89	0	0	1	0	0
CropRotYield_resi	0	-0.64	0	0	1	0
ProfitCrops	0	0	-0.43	0	0	1
ProfitCrops_slope	0.45	0	-0.28	1	0	1
ProfitCrops_resi	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nsurplus	0.11	0	-0.53	1	0	1
Nsurplus_slope	0	0	0.29	0	0	1
Nsurplus_resi	0	0.77	0	0	1	0

Table A6.8. Loadings and stability of explanatory variables associated with the selected sPLS-components in VK.

Explanatory variable	Loadings per component			Stability per component		
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	1 st	2 nd	3 rd
Area	0	0	0	0	0	0
AreaOwned	0	0	0	0	0	0
AreaCereals	0	0	0.43	0	0	1
AreaMainCrops	0	0	0	0	0	0
Intensity	0	0	-0.10	0	0	1
Labour	0.22	0	0	1	0	0
CPP	0	0	-0.39	0	0	1
Nitrogen	0.20	0	-0.56	1	0	1
Phosphate	0.53	0	-0.22	1	0	1
FarmManagement	0.17	0	0	1	0	0
AgeFarmer	0	0	0	0	0	0
Energy	0	0	-0.45	0	0	1
Depreciation	0	0	-0.27	0	0	1
OtherRevenue	0.05	0	0	1	0	0
OwnCapital	0	0	0	0	0	0
ModernityBuildings	0	0	0	0	0	0
ModernityMachinery	0	0	0	0	0	0
TotalCostsperha	-0.24	0	-0.11	1	0	1
TrueDiversity	0	0	0	0	0	0
Temperature_Spring	0	0.15	0	0	1	0
Precipitation_Spring	0	-0.18	0	0	1	0
Temperature_Summer	0	0	0	0	0	0
Precipitation_Summer	0	-0.03	0	0	1	0
PrecDef_Summer	0	0.13	0	0	1	0
PrecDef_Spring	0	0.36	0	0	1	0
Temperature	0	0	0	0	0	0
Precipitation	0	-0.30	0	0	1	0
PrecDef	0	0.38	0	0	1	0
ExtrPrec60_3	0	0	0	0	0	0
HWave	0	0.48	0	0	1	0
WarmWinter	0	0	0	0	0	0
WarmWet	0	0	0	0	0	0
D_Spring	0	0	0	0	0	0
D_Summer	0	0.58	0	0	1	0
WetHumPlant	0	0	0	0	0	0
WetHumGrow	0	0	0	0	0	0
WetHumHarv	0	0	0	0	0	0
OilPrice	-0.32	0	-0.01	1	0	1
FertilizerPrice	0	0	0	0	0	0
Landprice	-0.40	0	0	1	0	0

Interest	0.53	0	0	1	0	0
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Table A6.9. Average values of response variables, weather conditions and extreme events associated with the second sPLS-component in ZE. Values between brackets indicate the loading of variables on the component. Bold font of weather variables indicates above median weather conditions or occurrence of extreme events. Bold font of response variables indicates an above median absolute value. The bold font is applied to help evaluating whether extremes coincide with the most important weather condition (in this case "Heat wave").

	Nsurplus_resi kg/ha (- 0.77)	CropRotYield_resi 1000 kJ/ha (- 0.64)	Drought in summer # (0.58)	Heat wave # (- 0.48)	PrecDef mm/day (0.38)	PrecDef- Spring mm/day (0.36)	Precipitation (-0.30)	Precipitation_Spring (-0.18)	Temperature_Spring °C (0.15)	PrecDef_Summer mm/day (0.13)	Precipitation_ mm/day (-0.0
2006	1.8	-9807	0	1	0.2	1.6	1.8	1.5	12.7	1.0	2.2
2007	4.3	-5523	0	0	-0.6	1.1	2.5	2.0	14.3	-0.3	2.9
2008	6.8	654	0	0	-0.2	2.4	2.0	0.9	13.1	0.2	2.6
2009	-3.5	7422	0	0	0.0	1.6	1.9	1.6	13.4	1.1	1.9
2010	10.4	-11100	1	1	-0.4	1.8	2.2	1.2	11.6	-0.5	3.4
2011	5.7	469	0	0	-0.1	2.0	1.9	1.4	13.9	-0.4	2.9
2012	-10.7	9400	0	0	-0.3	0.9	2.0	1.9	12.2	0.4	2.5
2013	-8.3	1472	0	0	-0.1	0.9	1.9	1.8	11.5	0.9	2.1
2014	-15.7	18220	0	0	-0.0	0.4	1.9	1.4	13.5	1.0	1.9
2015	-10.2	-2684	0	1	-0.5	1.5	2.3	1.3	11.4	-0.3	3.1
2016	1.4	-489	0	0	0.0	0.8	1.7	2.1	13.2	1.4	1.4
2017	-8.2	24290	0	0	-0.4	1.5	2.2	1.5	13.3	-0.4	3.0
2018	31.5	-27954	1	1	0.8	1.9	1.3	1.5	15.1	2.5	1.0
2019	-1.1	-9889	0	1	0.2	2.2	1.8	1.2	13.2	1.2	2.0

Figure A6.7. sPLS model results for the first and second X-component in VK.

Figure A6.8. sPLS model results for the first and second Y-component in VK.

Figure A6.9. sPLS model results for the second and third X-component in VK.

Figure A6.10. sPLS model results for the second and third Y-component in VK.

Figure A6.11. Correlations between explanatory and response variables selected by the sPLS-model in VK.

Correlations in the original data
Among response variables

Figure A6.12. Correlations among response variables in FL.

Figure A6.13. Correlations among response variables in ZE.

Figure A6.14. Correlations among response variables in VK.

Among explanatory variables

Figure A6.15. Correlations among continuous explanatory data in FL. Dendrograms indicate groups with positively co-varying variables.

Figure A6.16. Correlations among continuous explanatory data in ZE. Dendrograms indicate groups with positively co-varying variables.

Figure A6.17. Correlations among continuous explanatory data in VK. Dendrograms indicate groups with positively co-varying variables.

Between explanatory and response variables

Figure A6.18. Correlations between continuous explanatory variables and response variables in FL. Dendrograms indicate groups with positively co-varying variables.

Figure A6.19. Correlations between continuous explanatory variables and response variables in ZE. Dendrograms indicate groups with positively co-varying variables.

Figure A6.20. Correlations between continuous explanatory variables and response variables in VK. Dendrograms indicate groups with positively co-varying variables.

Supplementary Materials 4.7. Additional sPLS-models

All fifteen response variables included

Performance

sPLS-model performance is lower with all fifteen response variables included. Especially the first component in FL and ZE has a low performance. The low Q2- and R2-scores for the first component in FL and ZE coincide with a relative large proportion of variation of X-Variables and Y-Variables explained. This implies that the dominant data structure in the Y-Variables is difficult to explain with the dominant data structure in the X-Variables. Instead, a less dominant structure in the X-Variables, represented by the second component, explains a moderate part of the Y-Variables in FL and ZE.

Table A7.11. Number of variables and performance per component of selected sPLS-models with all fifteen response variables.

Region	Component	Q2-score	R2-score	Number of variables kept		Variation explained	
				X-space	Y-space	X-space	Y-space
FL	1	0.058	0.112	2	5	0.138	0.200
	2	0.148	0.175	9	2	0.082	0.233
VK	1	0.172	0.226	9	2	0.171	0.218
	2	0.222	0.205	2	3	0.070	0.298
	3	0.098	0.106	9	5	0.092	0.147
ZE	1	-0.012	0.029	2	4	0.174	0.158
	2	0.099	0.195	4	2	0.081	0.193

Correlation plots

Figure A7.1. Correlation plot of projected data in an sPLS-model with fifteen response variables in FL.

Figure A7.2. Correlation plot of projected data in an sPLS-model with fifteen response variables in ZE.

Figure A7.3. Correlation plot of projected data in an sPLS-model with fifteen response variables in VK.

Interpretation

In all case studies, the first component is associated with at least one variable related to input intensity. In FL (and ZE), input intensity was associated with higher levels of profit of crops. In FL, higher input intensity was associated with lower specialization and lower levels of crop yields. In FL, additional crops in the rotation, such as onions and carrots are indeed relatively cost intensive, low in energy production, and have relatively high margins. In VK, input intensity was associated with the development of market prices. These are associated with decreasing slopes for output efficiency (also in PCA) and slopes of potato yields (absent in PCA).

The second component is in all case studies related to weather extremes and/or average weather conditions. In ZE and FL, these conditions and/or extremes are related to fluctuations in profit of crops and output efficiency. In VK, levels of crop yield and nitrogen surplus are affected by weather extremes.

In VK, the third component indicates that larger farms tend to have lower labour inputs, are managed by fewer managers and have lower intensity levels, possibly due to the relative higher use of modern machinery. Larger farms are subsequently related to higher profits per ha, higher output efficiencies, decreasing slopes of nitrogen surplus, slopes of potato yield and slopes of crop rotation yield.

Nine response variables related to crop rotation yield, nitrogen surplus and output efficiency

Performance

The performance of sPLS models including crop rotation yield, nitrogen surplus and output efficiency is lower for FL and VK, but higher for ZE. The interpretation of the sPLS-models is however almost identical to the sPLS models including profit of crops instead of output efficiency.

Interpretation

In all case studies, there is one component associated with weather conditions and residuals of nitrogen surplus (FL, VK), output efficiency (FL, ZE) and crop rotation yield (VK).

In FL, negative residuals of nitrogen surplus are mostly associated by drought in spring, or wet conditions later on in the growing period, while output efficiency is positively affected by heatwaves, and generally high temperatures in summer. Interestingly, in contrast with droughts in spring, precipitation deficiency in spring seems to be somewhat related with positive residuals of output efficiency and negative residuals of nitrogen surplus. In ZE, output efficiency is affected negatively by high temperatures, specifically in spring, which is also related to precipitation deficit in that season. Interestingly, farms in ZE seem to benefit from warm winters. The presence or absence of water in general and for both seasons is correlated to positive or negative residuals of crop rotation yields and contrasting residuals for nitrogen surplus in VK.

In all case studies, the other component is associated with at least one nutrient: phosphate (VK, FL) and nitrogen (ZE, FL). In FL and ZE, TrueDiversity is the main additional indicator. Farms in FL and ZE with more diverse crops are associated with larger and increasing nitrogen surpluses, larger crop rotation yield and decreasing output efficiency.

For VK, additional indicators are interest rates and landprices (trend!). Years with high phosphate input and high interest rates are associated with increasing output efficiency, increasing crop rotation yield, and high, but decreasing levels of nitrogen surplus. This is information that also could be concluded based on Figure 3 and the threshold regression.

Table 2. Number of variables and performance per component of selected sPLS-models with the nine response variables related to crop rotation yield, nitrogen surplus and output efficiency. All X-Variables included.

	Number of variables kept	Variation explained
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Region	Component	Q2-score	R2-score	X-space	Y-space	X-space	Y-space
FL	1	0.128	0.159	9	2	0.083	0.219
	2	0.097	0.135	4	5	0.094	0.182
VK	1	0.221	0.287	3	4	0.133	0.303
	2	0.266	0.240	8	2	0.097	0.279
ZE	1	0.096	0.318	5	2	0.091	0.196
	2	0.098	0.127	3	3	0.065	0.164

Excluding highly correlated explanatory variables.

Model performance dropped when excluding highly correlated explanatory variables from the dataset. Especially the performance of models in VK was still good.

Table 3. Number of variables and performance per component of selected sPLS-models with the nine response variables related to crop rotation yield, nitrogen surplus and profit of crops. Excluding highly correlated variables: weather variables for average yearly weather conditions, weather variables related to precipitation deficiency and farm variables CPP and Intensity.

Region	Component	Q2-score	R2-score	Number of variables kept		Variation explained	
				X-space	Y-space	X-space	Y-space
FL	1	0.100	0.140	2	2	0.096	0.149
	2	0.099	0.128	9	3	0.098	0.189
VK	1	0.196	0.265	9	5	0.140	0.259
	2	0.317	0.270	9	5	0.077	0.306
	3	0.149	0.083	8	2	0.116	0.168
ZE	1	0.083	0.166	5	2	0.066	0.203
	2	0.051	0.113	4	5	0.151	0.167

Supplementary Materials 4.8. Mixed models

Linear mixed models were applied as well, following the method as described in Bouttes et al. (2018) and Martin et al. (2017). However, models often did not converge, leading to a perfect correlation between intercept and slope. This is likely to lead to over or underestimation of observed levels in specific years. Moreover, for some observations residuals were not centred around zero which may lead to confounding variability with the observed levels of variables. Hence, a thorough checking of residuals per farm and the correlation between residuals and slopes seems necessary.

Figure A8.1. Scatterplots of slope and intercept of mixed model results on the response variables in the three case study areas.

Figure A8.2. Boxplots with residuals of mixed models for response variables in the three case study areas.